

Power Stair: A Piezoelectric Powered Stair as an Alternative Source of Energy During Emergency Power Outage

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Abstract

This proposal focuses on designing stairs with piezoelectric components that convert footsteps into electricity. It aims to evaluate the energy efficiency, load durability, and cost analysis of the system. This study used various testing methods, including measuring the energy output for efficiency, to determine whether the harvested power is stable enough to light up LEDs. Also, it utilized weight load tests to evaluate the piezoelectric materials' ability to resist deformation. Furthermore, employing cost analysis examined whether the technology offers practical benefits relative to its development expense, especially for emergency use. Piezoelectric with the dynamo can give an output of an average power of 58.46W every 10 steps, which is enough to power low-wattage LED bulbs for minimal durations. The durability test showed an average modulus of elasticity is 25.695 N/m², signifying that the materials can endure the mechanical pressure repeatedly without deformation. The total computed cost the prototype is ₱929, it confirms that the mechanism is feasible and

low-cost to build. Overall, the result illustrate that the Power Stair is a durable, cost-effective, and viable and emergency saver that is suitable for high-foot-traffic locations.

Key Words: Piezoelectric System, Sustainable Energy, Clean Energy, Microelectromechanical (MEMS), Electronics

Chapter I

This chapter of the research contains the introduction, research objectives, significance of the study, and scope and delimitations.

INTRODUCTION

Energy is essential for national progress, yet about 85% of global energy still comes from non-renewable sources such as coal, fuel, and natural gas. These are being consumed much faster than they can be naturally replenished, making them unsustainable in the long term (Oladeji, 2015). In the Philippines, most homes, industries, and institutions rely on these traditional energy sources, which makes the country vulnerable to power shortages and forced outages, especially during natural disasters or issues with supply (Baligad, 2024). This research highlights the urgent need for renewable energy solutions that support energy security while advancing United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 7: “Affordable and Clean Energy” (United Nations, 2023). It focuses on utilizing a piezoelectric system, which converts mechanical energy produced by humans into energy that can power electrical devices.

Piezoelectric microelectromechanical systems (PiezoMEMS) are attractive for developing next-generation self-powered microsystems. PiezoMEMS promises to eliminate the costly assembly for microsensors/microsystems and provide various mechanisms for recharging the batteries, thereby moving us closer towards batteryless wireless sensor systems and

networks. It is a response to the energy crisis, and the environment also calls for clean and green, reusable energy. And, in recent years, the development of smart devices has been rapid, and adaptation is widespread, where the change of battery is not convenient (Li & Lee, 2022).

In the study of Zhu, Yi, Yang, and Lee (2021), the piezoelectric effect occurs when mechanical stress is applied to certain solids, causing an electric charge to be generated, which produces electrical energy. This technology can be installed in the floors of overcrowded places, dancefloors, railway platforms, stairs, and in gym treadmills. However, its potential use as a backup power source for universities in the Philippines remains underexploited. Some designs even incorporated piezoelectric into inverters to help provide emergency electricity during emergency outages, which ensures the continuity of important operations (Aneja et al., 2016).

It is a device that generates many microwatts up to many watts per step, depending on the space, pedestrians' frequency, and piezoelectric technology (Elhalwagy, 2017). Although there are a number of earnest research studies that have focused on harvesting power from piezoelectric floor tiles, the piezoelectric application is still hindered by many factors, which lead to the deprivation of the advantages of this technology. The research addresses how to get the Maximum benefits from a piezoelectric energy harvesting floor in Buildings' interior spaces, according to

the various weights of every usage factor, and through the integration of different kinds of piezoelectric technology capabilities.

This research aims to address the gap by proposing the “Power Stair” system, a piezoelectric-powered staircase, to be implemented at Bulacan State University (BulSU). With its large population, it provides an ideal environment for capturing mechanical energy and turning it into a reliable emergency power source. The energy collected can be used to power essential systems during blackouts, such as emergency lighting or device charging stations, helping reduce interruptions in all campus operations.

To sum it up, this research aims to contribute to enhancing energy resilience and support SDG 7 by promoting renewable energy for decarbonization, energy security, and economic growth (Strielkowski et al., 2021). This proposal also addresses the limited research and application of piezoelectric energy systems as emergency power solutions in Philippine universities. Therefore, not only does this study support sustainability, but it also allows students, especially those who are in engineering and technological fields, to develop innovative solutions to solve real-world energy issues. This establishes BulSU as a standard for energy resilience and sustainability among academic institutions.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

This study aims to develop a stair design

with piezoelectric components that convert the force of footsteps into an alternative source of electricity. The first aspect is to investigate how effective, dependable, and eco-friendly the system can be once implemented. The investigation observes the amount of energy that can be collected from regular stair usage, then evaluates whether the energy is stable enough to light up small emergency devices such as LEDs, and whether the system can maintain consistent performance during actual situations. The result can help determine whether the system is reliable to power the light in a power outage or an emergency.

This study also focuses on evaluating the amount of weight the piezoelectric can endure. The researchers aim to measure the durability of materials to withstand frequent use and their weight capacity, which they can hold without breaking, since the stairs are often stepped on by stakeholders with different body weights and at varying frequencies.

Furthermore, this study also aims to assess the expenses and upkeep requirements of the piezoelectric. The total cost of the system and its maintenance is considered to show if the product can be a practical option during an emergency power outage, while also being affordable and durable for long-term use.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

In the face of serious and ongoing environmental issues, there is a demand for cleaner alternatives. Electricity generated through mechanical force presents a more

sustainable option. This research aims to help people obtain sustainable electricity resources while preserving the orderliness of the environment. The following individuals and groups may benefit from this study:

Students and Instructors. This research may encourage both students and instructors to utilize renewable energy. Instructors may also integrate this topic into their lessons to raise awareness and guide students in using energy responsibly. Knowing that they are helping the environment may then motivate them to use these stairs instead of elevators, offering a quick form of exercise, as they often have no time. The stored electricity may also aid these individuals who, hopefully, do not have to experience power outages, since such outages are inevitable and unpredictable.

University Administration and Maintenance Staff. Understanding the advantages of using a cleaner energy source may empower the school administrators and maintenance staff to start the implementation and installation of such systems. Its ability to store electricity might also help them prepare for and respond to power outages without unnecessary delay.

Local Government Units. Foot traffic is common in public places. This study may encourage the local government to address this problem and implement the piezoelectric system, making use of the mechanical energy produced by daily

movement.

Environment Advocates. Piezoelectric power is recognized as a clean electricity source. They may use this study to promote energy conservation and encourage participation to create a cleaner environment. By powering stairs and storing energy for emergency use, advocates may further influence individuals to protect the environment.

Future Researchers and Developers. As the world continues to evolve, toward either a cleaner or more polluted future, this study may offer a foundation for future researchers to further explore the concept of piezoelectric energy. They may then collaborate with developers who share the same purpose to improve the electrical output and expand the use of this system across wider areas, which can generate higher mechanical energy.

SCOPE AND DELIMITATION

This study aims to develop and test a piezoelectric-powered stair system that can turn the everyday pressure of footsteps into usable electricity, especially during emergency power outages. Specifically, it seeks to evaluate the efficiency of the energy system if used in real situations. Moreover, the durability of the materials is considered in terms of weight load. Finally, examine cost and maintenance concerns, since these are important factors in applying the system to real infrastructure.

Furthermore, to conduct the study, the

product is to be tested at Bulacan State University–Main Campus, Natividad Hall, during the second semester of the academic year of 2025-2026. The researchers are to create a formal letter of permission from the dean to use the place for product testing. Additionally, researchers are not conducting a survey questionnaire to find consumer satisfaction, as its purpose is to test the product only. It utilizes a qualitative approach, where its qualities are observed and analyzed. Moreover, due to the lack of budget, the study cannot fully test certain factors like long-term safety, durability under heavy use, or how the system would perform with better quality materials. These areas remain outside the current scope, but they are acknowledged as important and may be explored in future research.

Chapter II

This chapter presents the relevant theories, the related literature and studies being utilized in the study.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Piezoelectric Effect Theory. In the study of Zhu, Yi, Yang, and Lee (2021), Piezoelectric refers to the induction of electrical charges that accumulate in particular solid materials in which leads to the polarization of their electric dipole when a mechanical pressure is applied.

This indicates that the Piezoelectric Effect uses mechanical pressure to create

electrical energy. This alternative source of energy can be implemented on a stepping platform, specifically, a stair where multiple people step on to climb floors.

Theory of Electromechanical Conversion.

This theory, as defined in the book of Krause et al. (2013), utilizes magnetic or electric fields for coupling, and then the device transforms energy from electrical to mechanical form. It describes how electrical input results in mechanical output, which is based on principles of energy balance and electromagnetism.

This theory relates to the piezoelectric effect theory, whereas mechanical energy is used to generate electricity by electromagnetic induction. Additionally, it supports the context of using the stairs to produce electricity by utilizing the mechanical pressure when stepped on.

RELATED LITERATURE

According to EnergySage (2023), solar energy often uses panels, which take a considerable amount of space to properly harvest the energy from the sun, typically ranging from 5-10square meters per kilowatt. Following this, the generated energy is also dependent on time to optimize the power source fully. Whereas in utilizing wind energy. According to Stehly et al. (2024), wind uses large-scale turbines to harness the energy from the wind typically costs 1.3-2.2million dollars per megawatt, and also requires spacious areas. Both energy harvesting sources often require high-cost maintenance to keep the

production of renewable energy.

As stated by Gaber & AbdelRaheem (2025), Piezoelectric energy however, is a more straightforward approach whilst being cost-efficient, as piezoelectric energy can take advantage of urban areas such as sidewalks to generate a proper amount of renewable energy without taking too much space, and because piezoelectric energy can be down-scaled, maintaining the devices that harness piezoelectric energy is lower than those in conventional renewable energy sources. Many associated studies on piezoelectric energy have verified many practical limits that hinder its best performance, especially in crowded or traffic areas.

The controversial challenge is the very low electrical output of each piezoelectric, which normally gives only minimal voltages under human footsteps, proving the output is not enough to power devices without adding a mechanical booster or power storage components (Zheuan et al., 2023). Moreover, previous designs before were prone to physical wear and tear, as pressure often caused the sensors to break or experience a loss of sensitivity over time, particularly when placed under hard floors (Li et al., 2022).

To achieve practical implementation of this technology, a fully assembled energy harvester on the order of a quarter-sized dollar coin (diameter=24.26 mm, thickness=1.75 mm) should be able to generate about 100 μ W continuous power from low-frequency ambient vibrations

(below 100 Hz) (Priya, et al. 2019).

Some research also notes the unequal energy distribution, where different weights and walking styles led to unpredictable energy and to fluctuate wildly (Zhu et al., 2021). These shortcomings led us to innovations. The addition of a plywood layer that is supported by springs facilitates the force of each step to reduce the damage to the sensor, while the inclusion of a gear rack-dynamo mechanism boosts the output of the piezoelectric to solve the persistent problem of being low power. Furthermore, by performing another durability and energy efficiency tests, the current work explicitly tackles issues of durability and output stability in previous literature. Therefore, the “Power Stair” system uses a new structure and solution to the electrical problem that has been developed in answer to the limitations noted in earlier piezoelectric floor and stair designs.

DEFINITION OF TERMS

Deformation. Pertains to the alteration in the framework of the piezoelectric material when pressure is applied through every step. In this study, deformation implies how the piezoelectric sensor compresses to produce an electric charge.

Microelectromechanical (MEMS). Refers to microelectromechanical systems, which unite mechanical and electrical components at a miniscale. In this study, MEMS relates to a piezoelectric microstructure that allows the alteration of small-scale vibration in

mechanics or motions on the stairs into electrical energy that is functional.

Mechanical Stress. The exert pressure on the piezoelectric when someone walks on the stairs. Stress is the main energy source that activates the effect of piezoelectric, changing mechanical energy into electrical output.

Decarbonization. The method of decreasing carbon dioxide discharges by converting from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources.

Cleaner Alternatives. Eco-friendly energy options that lessen pollution, instead of fuel combustion, the power stair acts as a cleaner source, using the energy from the footsteps instead of fuel combustion.

Electric Dipole. A pair of opposite electric charges in the piezoelectric components that rearrange when under pressure to produce an electric output.

Coupling. The connection between electrical and mechanical energy, where the force that is applied on the stair changes into electricity through the piezoelectric system..

Electromagnetism. The analysis of magnetism and electricity describes how pressure from a footstep produces electrical energy through electromagnetic and piezoelectric effects.

Electromagnetic Induction. Involves the process where a changing magnetic field induces current, facilitating the theory of motion-based electricity generation.

Oscilloscope. A measuring device that shows voltage output from the sensors to assess energy stability and accuracy.

Elastic Modulus. A material property indicating resistance to deformation, utilized to evaluate the components of piezoelectrics when it comes to durability under pressure.

Chapter III

This chapter presents the methods and techniques of the study, research design, and data collection techniques.

RESEARCH DESIGN

In this study, a Qualitative research design is used. The focus was on evaluating the product's qualities, like energy efficiency, load-bearing durability, and cost efficiency. The data were processed and interpreted, and were supported by grounded theories.

The Power Stair project really focuses on creating and testing out a tech prototype. It makes sure to highlight a qualitative research approach on purpose. The whole study goes beyond just checking the numbers for how the piezoelectric system performs. It also digs into the ways users handle the stairs. How do they view its practical value? And how this prototype holds up in everyday settings.

Including energy output, durability testing, and cost analysis—these measurements alone cannot capture the everyday usability and human experience of encountering and using a piezoelectric-powered stair. Early prototypes often need more than

performance data; they require insight into how people respond to the design, what aspects feel intuitive or confusing, how safe or comfortable the system appears, and how users imagine it functioning during emergencies. These forms of understanding are best explored through qualitative methods.

Approaches such as user observation, informal feedback sessions, guided walkthroughs, and short interviews offer detailed, grounded descriptions of the user experience. These methods help the research team notice issues that quantitative tests cannot reveal—such as hesitation in stepping, concerns about stability, uncertainty about how the system works, or suggestions for improving the design. This kind of insight is essential for refining the prototype and ensuring it aligns with user needs and real-world expectations.

RESEARCH LOCALE

Bulacan State University was specified as the test site not only because of its population but also due to its favorable structural design and environmental settings. The establishment of the university such as E library and Natividad Hall where people are going up and down are equipped with durable stairways with conventional step height and design, offering steady mechanical pressure that gives reliable data of the piezoelectric efficiency. These stairs can adapt to the placement of sensors and wiring while sustaining the heaviness and foot traffic. Moreover, the continuous movement of every stakeholder on different

floors maintains regular usage, assessing it in real-time conditions to measure the energy output and verify the mechanism's capability under different load conditions.

Additionally, the university's facility makes it possible for systematic experimentation while ensuring a genuine environmental setting that depicts usual daily use. This makes BulSU an optimal premise to evaluate the stability and the conversion capability of the Power Stair prototype. Ensuring the measurement integrity of the results, two weeks are administered for data collection, facilitating the researchers to evaluate load resistance, the power it provides, and its overall dependability through various testing intervals. In this period, persistent observation of productivity trends assures that the data collected by researchers properly conveys the stairway's functional use within the university's regular operation.

MATERIALS

Piezoelectric is a material that can convert mechanical stress or pressure into an electric charge.

Figure 1. Piezoelectric

<https://share.google/images/kiMhiYf3qghUzQ>

LvS

A **spring metal** is a metal with a spring mechanism that maintains consistent contact between the materials.

Figure 2. Spring Metal
<https://sl.bing.net/H99rqXCB4u>

Plywood is a stacked veneer wood, a lightweight and shatter-resistant material commonly used in various applications.

Figure 3. 12mm Plywood
<https://sl.bing.net/irhnqeBbU8y>

Electrical wire is essential for safely conducting electricity in various applications, usually made from copper or aluminum.

Figure 4. Wire
<https://sl.bing.net/frxW0rMVoa>

NiMH batteries, or Nickel-Metal Hydride batteries, are rechargeable batteries known for their high energy density and safety.

Figure 5. NiMH Battery
<https://sl.bing.net/gxCNYn1KsP6>

A **capacitor** is a device used to hold and let out energy, typically used for smoothing, filtering, and energy storage in circuits.

Figure 6. Capacitor

A **diode bridge** is an electrical circuit that has four diodes set up to change alternating current (AC) into direct current (DC) by enabling the energy or the current to flow in one direction.

Figure 7. Diode Bridge
<https://sl.bing.net/jMjSTHB1dx6>

A **MOSFET** is a fast and efficient electronic switch, triggered by a control voltage applied at its gate terminal.

Figure 8. Trigger Circuit MOSFET
<https://sl.bing.net/cvhT6XJXYSi>

A **gear rack** is a material that transfers a linear movement to rotational movement. This is used to rotate a sprocket and a dynamo.

Figure 9. Gear Rack
<https://sl.bing.net/do5Y9WlG1cm>

A **sprocket** is a wheel that has teeth and is primarily used for rotational movement with chains or rackets.

Figure 10. Sprocket
<https://sl.bing.net/jlf7RHc1AXI>

A **dynamo** is another electric device that converts mechanical energy into electrical energy. This material was used as a supplement to increase the product's output.

Figure 11. Dynamo
<https://sl.bing.net/keOjwwS0Ei4>

A **rubber bellows tube** is a material with an elastic spring-like structure. This is used as a casing for the springs to prevent them from moving sideways.

Figure 12. Rubber Bellows Tube
<https://sl.bing.net/kAWyNMFosMe>

PROCEDURE FOR THE PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT

To integrate the product, the researcher needed numerous piezoelectric sensors to put above the stair flooring. The plywood was used to receive footsteps or direct contact from the foot of a person. Meanwhile, the spring is in the middle of the piezoelectric, and the plywood absorbed the force. At the same time, it stops the plywood from contacting the piezo. The force traveled from the plywood to the spring until it reached the piezo, which converts it into energy. Additionally,

a gear rack was attached to the plywood, while a dynamo and sprocket were attached at the base. The applied force pushed the gear rack down, which made the sprocket and dynamo rotate. This served as an additional energy output.

The piezoelectric wire and the dynamo were connected and soldered into a high-voltage wire so that it can accommodate a slightly higher voltage and not look messy. The wire is also connected to the battery so that it can be preserved. The battery was then connected to some of the LED bulbs or emergency lights, and the MOSFET activated automatically in case of an emergency.

Through the capacitor, the bulbs remained steadily lit overnight or for a period until the preserved energy runs out without flashing. The diode bridge was connected to the wire of the piezoelectric and the wire of the battery to convert the energy from AC to DC.

Figure 13. Power Stair's Prototype Illustration

DATA COLLECTION

Energy Efficiency Test. This study adapted the method from the study of Tao et al. (2024), whereas the harvested energy current and voltage of the Piezoelectric was measured using a device called an oscilloscope after a sensor collected a displacement signal. Before each session, the oscilloscope was reset to factory defaults, ports were cleaned, and probes were inspected. Probe attenuation was checked and matched to channel settings. The internal calibration signal was performed and repeated to verify vertical, horizontal scaling, and trigger levels. Environmental factors, such as humidity and electromagnetic interference, were monitored after each trial set to ensure consistency (Fluke, 2025).

The displacement sensor was positioned directly under the stepping area and connected to the oscilloscope with shielded cables to minimize electrical noise. LED bulbs of 3W, 6W, 10W, 15W, and 20W were connected individually through a switch box, allowing easy changes in load. The step location was marked with tape, and the researcher used the same footwear for all trials, maintaining a consistent stepping rhythm.

The force of each step was measured and recorded using a calibrated load cell to ensure consistency during testing. The load cell was zeroed before testing, and standardized weights (e.g., 5 kg, 10 kg, 15

ILLUSTRATION OF THE PROTOTYPE

kg) were used to verify linear response. A three-point calibration covering low, medium, and high loads was performed, with recalibration if measurements deviate beyond.

For each LED wattage, the researcher performed ten consistent steps, recording the voltage, current waveforms, and step force from the load cell. After completing the steps, the duration the LED remains lit was measured, and the process was repeated on three separate days to account for environmental variations.

The researchers oversaw each trial: one recording measurements and the other monitoring step consistency. All data were time-stamped and exported in non-editable formats. Irregularities, such as missteps or unstable signals, were logged. Trials with more than 10% variation in step force were discarded. A laboratory notebook was used to document trial conditions, including temperature, humidity, and footwear.

Weight Load Durability Test. This study followed the methodology outlined by Li et al. (2022), in which the mechanical performance of the piezoelectric material is evaluated using a Material Testing System (MTS) machine under various weight loads.

Consideration for the daily foot traffic

The researcher considered the daily foot traffic in Natividad Hall of Bulacan State University as a variable that may affect the data during the testing of Energy efficiency and Weight load durability. Natividad Hall is a five-story building used by the College of Engineering. With 8 departments of engineering, the enrolled freshmen have a

total of 1,081, while there are 963 sophomores in their second year, 951 in their third year, and 1,400 graduating students in their fourth year. Thus, it has a total of 4,396 students enrolled in the College of Engineering for the academic year 2025-2026. By using the formula of combination with repetition $\frac{(n+r-1)!}{r!(n-1)!}$, we can get the at least total variation of the daily foot traffic at Natividad Hall.

Cost Analysis. This study conducted a cost analysis of the product to examine the system's overall cost and its reliability as an alternative source of energy, emphasizing its practicality and utility in emergency cases.

Sample Size and Statistical Considerations

The data in the study were collected from the three repeated trials, each comprising ten steps, which were used as the functional prototype for calculating the power output. While this served as initial data, the sample size is still insufficient and does not fully accommodate the full range of motion in a person's footstep, the variety of weights, and the daily step count. A more comprehensive data set improved the reliability of the statistical analysis and reduced uncertainty when calculating the actual mean performance of the mechanism. Further work increased the trial count and included different weights to have a wider representative distribution of force applications

DATA ANALYSIS

Energy Efficiency. The data gathered from the piezoelectric stairs was analyzed by monitoring the amount of voltage and current produced each time the stairs were used. The collected values were multiplied to determine the power (power = current × voltage) (Tao et al., 2024). To ensure the repeatability and reliability of the energy, the mean, standard deviation, and the coefficient of variation was computed. The coefficient of variation is a measurement that expresses the ratio of Standard Deviation to the Mean, which is useful for analyzing variability and for comparing sets of data in terms of stability or consistency (GeeksforGeeks, 2025). To calculate the coefficient of variation, the standard deviation was divided by the mean (CV = SD/mean); the lower percent of CV implies the less variability there is in the mean (Bobbitt, 2021). Therefore, a CV lower than 10% was used for this study.

Weight Load Durability. The data collected from the Material Testing System (MTS) machine was used to get the elastic modulus of the product. Elastic modulus is necessary in assessing the piezoelectric materials' resistance to deformation under stress and using the formula $E' = FH/SL$, where the elastic modulus (E') is equal to the product of the vertical load (F) and the height (H) of the piezoelectric device, divided by the surface area (S) of the plywood, multiplied by the vertical displacement (L). The result was compared to the standard elastic modulus of 2.04×10^{10} N/m² from Piezo Systems and Mide Technology (2020).

The daily foot traffic variable

By using the formula of combination with repetition $\frac{(n+r-1)!}{r!(n-1)!}$, where n is the total amount of population and r is the number of repetitions. With a population of 4,396 and a repetition of 5 since Natividad Hall is a five-story building, we can then substitute the values in the formula $\frac{(4,396+5-1)!}{5!(4,396-1)!}$. Therefore, the computed total variation of the daily traffic in Natividad Hall is at least **13,710,758,432,750,880 steps** on stairs.

Cost Analysis. The researchers conducted the cost-effectiveness analysis of Shi & Nambudiri (2017), which is used to analyze and interpret the benefit of a new technology or product compared to its development cost. Specifically, whether the Innovation or an alternative option gives a significant return on investment (Shi & Nambudiri, 2017). This method analyzed the maintenance of the Power Stairs to make it practical and cost-effective, especially during emergencies.

Since the project involves electrical wiring and batteries embedded in the staircase, there is a potential risk of short circuits, battery overheating, and slipping accidents. To ensure safety, all electrical wires were fully insulated. Moreover, Sonic Electric (2024) explained that proper electrical insulation using quality wires can help prevent accidental short circuits and overheating. The surface of the stairs was covered with an anti-slip material to reduce the risk of falls. Additionally, Allelco (2024) stated that NiMH batteries should be managed carefully using protective circuits

to prevent overcharging or overheating. To further enhance safety, a MOSFET circuit was installed as suggested by Amazon (2025), which can regulate voltage flow efficiently in high-power applications. Regular inspection every six months is also recommended to check for any loose wires, damaged parts, or cracks on the surface. These safety measures helped maintain both electrical reliability and user protection even without direct safety testing.

Figure 1. Chart for the data on energy harvested per step.

The chart above presents the harvested energy power in watts per ten steps. This was repeated for three attempts, and is averaged for accuracy. According to the data given in the table, in the three attempts, a power of 58.43W, 58.47W, and 58.49W was harvested. It has an average power of 58.46W per 10 steps. According to Elektrotechnik, the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC 60038) has classifications for the levels of voltages, and these are: the extra high voltage, which has more than 230kV of AC; the high voltage, which has 35kV to 230kV; the medium voltage, which has 1kV to 35kV; the low voltage, which has between 70V to 1kV of AC; and the extra-low voltage, which has lower than 70V of AC. Therefore, the results imply that it is classified as an extra-low voltage.

Chapter IV

This chapter presents the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the resulting data collected from the testing methods.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION

1. Energy Efficiency Test

Presented in this section is the result of the energy efficiency test conducted by the researchers.

Figure 2. Table for the time it takes to deplete the harvested energy.

The figure shows the result of the time it takes to deplete the harvested energy using 3W, 6W, 10W, 15W, and 20W light bulbs. This was repeated for three attempts for each type of light bulbs, and was averaged to get an accurate result. The time it took to deplete the harvested energy was 57.96s for the 3W bulb, 28.95s for the 6W bulb, 17.35s for the 10W bulb, 11.53s for the 15W bulb, and 8.66W for the 20W bulb. As the power of the bulb increases, the time it takes to deplete the harvested energy decreases. This indicates that a lower power bulb should be used for longer use.

2. Weight Load Durability Test

Figure 3. Elastic Modulus of Power Stair

The figure above shows the elastic modulus of the product in three attempts and its average. In which a pressure of 25.430 N/m², 25.542 N/m², and 25.113 N/m² which has an average of 25.695 N/m². According to Piezo Systems and Mide Technology (2020), the standard elastic modulus of a piezoelectric is 2.04x10¹⁰ N/m². This means that the product exceeds the standard elastic modulus and still works after being applied with a strong force.

Energy Efficiency and Weight Load Durability Data Conclusion

Despite the average energy output per ten steps being 58.46 W, minor differences were observed in every trial, indicating the range of normal motion under pressure. We consider this result as normal, as this kind of variation is expected outside or in the real world, where people have multiple weight differences, walking styles, and stepping forces. Higher fluctuations may influence the dependability of accumulated energy and emphasize the necessity of capacitors to smooth voltage fluctuations. The mechanism's output was acceptably consistent in the testing area, but real-world use would require better stabilization for better performance.

3. Cost Analysis

Cost-Effectiveness Analysis: Power Stairs		
Product	Materials	Price
Power Stairs	Piezoelectric	₱32
	Spring metal	₱35
	Plywood	₱80
	Electrical wire	₱49
	NiMH batteries	₱51
	Capacitor	₱44
	Diode bridge	₱48
	Mosfet	₱82
	Gear rack	₱278
	Sprocket	₱50
	Dynamo	₱180
Total		₱929

The cost analysis focuses on determining whether the Power Stair prototype is economically practical by examining only the materials listed in the cost table. The total material cost amounts to ₱929, which includes the piezoelectric sensor, spring metal, plywood, electrical wiring, NiMH battery, capacitor, diode bridge, MOSFET, gear rack, sprocket, and dynamo. According to Shi and Nambudiri (2017), cost-effectiveness analysis evaluates whether the long-term benefits provided by

a new technology justify its development cost. In this case, the Power Stair's ability to generate energy from daily foot traffic provides continuous, low-maintenance power that may offer long-term value during emergency outages.

According to Li and Lee (2021), piezoelectric components generally have a lifespan of 5 to 8 years, depending on environmental conditions and frequency of use. Meanwhile, Allelco (2024) explained that NiMH batteries typically require replacement every 2 to 3 years due to natural charge degradation. Other electronic parts, such as capacitors and diodes, can last up to 10 years if properly maintained. Routine maintenance should be done every six months to inspect wiring, connections, and sensor performance to ensure long-term stability.

When compared to the other backup energy solutions, such as fuel-powered generators or solar panels, the Power Stair offers a cleaner, quieter, and more sustainable alternative. As Oladeji (2015) discussed, fuel-based power systems emit pollutants and contribute to environmental degradation, while Strielkowski et al. (2021) emphasized that renewable technologies support sustainable energy development. Moreover, Aneja et al. (2016) highlighted that piezoelectric systems generate power from human movement, making them a practical and eco-friendly alternative. Therefore, the Power Stair can be considered a cost-efficient and environmentally friendly backup energy

solution suitable for long-term use.

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, and RECOMMENDATION

SUMMARY

This study integrates and analyzes the Power Stair, a piezoelectric-powered staircase is made to transform footsteps into useful electric energy for emergency outages of power. The mechanism was built using the piezoelectric, spring, plywood dynamo, metal, and other necessary electrical components such as MOSFETs, diode bridge, Capacitor, and NiMH batteries. The study's goal is to discover the system's energy performance, durability under load, and affordability. A qualitative design was used, and the trial was accomplished at Bulacan State University in Natividad Hall so the researcher could emulate real foot traffic conditions.

Collected Data through the output of energy that is measured, tests in durability using elastic modulus, and the assessment of the cost of the components and materials that are used. The outcome showed that the Piezoelectric with the dynamo can give an output of an average power of 58.46W every 10 steps, which is enough to power low-wattage LED bulbs for minimal durations. The durability test showed an average modulus of elasticity is 25.695 N/m², signifying that the materials can endure the mechanical pressure repeatedly without deformation. The total computed cost of the prototype is ₱929, which confirms that the

mechanism is feasible and low-cost to build. Overall, the results illustrate that the Power Stair is a durable, cost-effective, and viable emergency saver that is suitable for high-foot-traffic locations.

CONCLUSION

The study illustrates that having piezoelectric in facilities such as stairways can give a significant aid during emergency energy needs in an eco-friendly way. Although Power Stair is incomparable to major power systems, its capability to transform regular foot traffic into useful energy shows that even small, passive power harvesting solutions can enhance energy readiness without depending on outside power sources. This emphasizes the efficiency of using human movement as an accessible and renewable energy input. Beyond its functional capability, the project highlights the inclusive potential of micro energy systems in public institutions. Its affordability, durability, and efficiency make it a feasible solution to foot traffic environments where continuous operations are necessary. More importantly, the Power Stair acts as a foundation for future innovations, showing that minimal, growable, and sustainable technologies can advance long-term environmental resilience.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results and the limits of this study, there are a few suggestions for future researchers on the piezoelectric-powered stair system.

First, it is better to use higher-quality material, such as an acrylic sheet, as a foot

hold instead of plywood, since it can affect the performance of the product and protect the wiring from moisture.

Second, the testing period should be longer so that you can try different setups and designs, like changing the wiring placement of the piezo, and test which is better and produces more energy can be observed over time.

Third, In the part of the gearing under the plate, it would be better if there were more gearing, so it revolves for more energy output

Fourth, a bearing should be installed inside the gears to increase their rotation drastically. Making the gear a little bit smaller would increase its rotation. It enhances the look of the product if the gearings are hidden.

Lastly, all concerns that were not covered in this study, such as efficiency and heavy use, need to be tested carefully. It is recommended that the product be evaluated by experts in engineering and energy systems and tested in the laboratory using energy auditing (energy assessment) to ensure its reliability in the field.

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